

Date: Aug 27 2018 10:28:32:023AM
To: "Ann Lebeck" alebeck65@gmail.com
From: "CJSM" jonathan.scovner@wolterskluwer.com
Subject: Review Outcome

RE: CJSM-18-410, entitled "Case Report
Platelet Rich Plasma: A new treatment option for a Morel-Lavallee lesion"

Dear Dr. Lebeck,

Many thanks for submitting your manuscript to the Clinical Journal of Sport Medicine for consideration of publication.

I am sorry to say that a 'reject' decision has been made at this stage.

I'm not sure that this Case Report is likely to lead to a change in clinical management for patients with these lesions. PRP has been used for a wide variety of injuries, but clinical efficacy is often difficult to assess. It is impossible to tell whether or not the PRP really helped in this case.

We thank you for submitting your work to our Journal, and hope that you will continue to do so in the future.

Best Wishes,

Dr Christopher Hughes
Editor-in-Chief, Clinical Journal of Sport Medicine

<https://cjsm.editorialmanager.com/>

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